

Photochemical looping strategy for concentrated ammonia synthesis via carbon monoxide mediated ambient nitrogen fixation

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ABSTRACT

Ammonia is a cornerstone of fertilizers and an emerging carbon-free energy carrier, yet its industrial synthesis via Haber–Bosch consumes ~1% of global energy. Photocatalytic nitrogen fixation provides a potential alternative, but conventional processes operate in aqueous media and yield trace concentrations of ammonia that are impractical to collect and use. Here, we introduce a photochemical looping strategy that integrates nitrogen activation, reduction, and solid-state capture in a cyclic process. Using a Pt–heteropolyacid–TiO₂ composite, carbon monoxide, either supplied directly or produced in situ from CO₂, generates oxygen vacancies on the heteropolyacid that adsorb and activate N₂, while water supplies protons and regenerates the vacancies. The formed ammonia is stored as a stable ammonium salt, which can be released upon calcination to produce aqueous NH₃ solutions up to 1.3 wt%, which is significantly higher than the typically reported concentrations in the direct photocatalytic N₂ reduction in aqueous suspensions. By coupling photocatalysis with solid-state storage, this looping approach overcomes long-standing barriers in conversion, selectivity, and product recovery, establishing a scalable framework for solar-driven ammonia production under mild conditions.

1. Introduction

Nitrogen gas (N₂) makes up about 78% volume of the Earth's atmosphere and it is a virtually inexhaustible reservoir of elemental nitrogen [1–3]. Its robust N≡N triple bond (941 kJ/mol) makes it too inert to participate easily in most natural and industrial processes [4]. In nature, biological nitrogen fixation by microbes maintains the ecosystems, and in industry, the Haber-Bosch process (HBP) can catalytically reduce N₂ with H₂ into ammonia (NH₃) under harsh conditions (673–873 K, 15–25 MPa) via an iron-based catalyst promoted with K₂O and Al₂O₃ (Fig. 1) [5–7]:

NH₃, as the precursor to nitrogen-based fertilizers, sustains almost 50% of global food production and is considered for the design of future fuels or hydrogen storage. With increasing population and technological development, NH₃ production struggles to keep up with demand, while the Haber–Bosch process consumes around 1% of global energy and contributes to greenhouse gas emissions [8–10].

Photocatalytic N₂ fixation provides a potential green alternative that can harness solar energy to drive NH₃ synthesis under ambient conditions. Usually, oxygen vacancies (O_v) play the key role in catalysts to weaken the N≡N bond via back-donation into nitrogen π* orbitals, thereby facilitating the first proton-coupled electron transfer step (*N₂ → NNH). For example, studies incorporating oxygen vacancies in BiOCl, BiOI, In₂O₃, and related materials have demonstrated enhanced N₂

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adsorption and activation at exposed facets, resulting in an improved NH_4^+ productivity [11–16]. However, the efficiency remains limited by several points: (1) weak adsorption and inefficient activation of N_2 on the catalyst surfaces; (2) sluggish nitrogen bond cleavage stemming from inadequate proton sources and delayed transfer into intermediates ($^*\text{NNH}$, $^*\text{NNH}_2$, $^*\text{NH}$, $^*\text{NH}_2$); and (3) rapid recombination of photo-generated electron-hole pairs. This usually results in a low concentration of ammonia in the product solution (typically <10–100 ppm) [17–20] (Table S1, SI). This makes separation, storage, and practical use nearly impossible, regardless of mechanistic advances in N_2 activation.

Here we report a photochemical looping strategy that integrates N_2 reduction with solid-state trapping of ammonia (Fig. 1). Using a Pt–phosphotungstic acid– TiO_2 composite, CO, which is a well-known gas used in Fischer–Tropsch synthesis [21,22] and many catalytic reactions, either supplied directly or generated from CO_2 , forms oxygen vacancies that adsorb and activate N_2 , while water provides protons and regenerates these vacancies. Crucially, the formed NH_3 is immediately protonated and stored as stable ammonium phosphotungstate, preventing loss and enabling its subsequent release as a concentrated aqueous NH_3 solution (up to 1.3 wt%). This concentration is significantly higher than in typical photocatalytic reports and achieved with > 99% ammonia selectivity (Table S1, SI). Using UV–Vis spectroscopy with the corresponding colorimetric reagent, we did not detect any other nitrogen products [23]. Mechanistic investigations and DFT reveal a vacancy-mediated, hydrazine-type pathway. By addressing the intertwined challenges of activation, selectivity, and separation, this looping approach opens a path to scalable, solar-driven nitrogen fixation.

2. Methods

2.1. Chemicals

Aluminum oxide (Al_2O_3) was purchased from Alfa Aesar. Other chemicals including chloroplatinic acid hexahydrate ($\text{H}_2\text{PtCl}_6 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\geq 37.50\%$ Pt basis), palladium(II) chloride (PdCl_2 , $\geq 99\%$ trace metals basis), copper(II) chloride (CuCl_2 , $\geq 99.9\%$ trace metals basis), nickel(II) chloride (NiCl_2 , $\geq 99.9\%$ trace metals basis), cesium (I) nitrate (CsNO_3 , $\geq 99.9\%$ trace metals basis), zinc(II) oxide (ZnO , powder, <5 μm particle size, $\geq 99\%$ trace metals basis), ammonium chloride (NH_4Cl , ACS reagent, $\geq 99.5\%$), phosphotungstic acid hydrate ($\text{H}_3[\text{P}(\text{W}_3\text{O}_{10})_4] \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$, abbreviated as HPW, reagent grade), phosphomolybdic acid hydrate ($\text{H}_3[\text{P}(\text{Mo}_3\text{O}_{10})_4] \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$, abbreviated as HPMo, ACS reagent), tungstosilicic acid hydrate ($\text{H}_4[\text{Si}(\text{W}_3\text{O}_{10})_4] \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$, abbreviated as HSiW, $\geq 99.9\%$ trace metals basis), titanium dioxide (TiO_2 , P25, $\geq 99.5\%$ trace

metals basis), sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4 , ACS reagent, 95.0–98.0%), ammonium hydroxide solution (NH_4OH , ACS reagent, 28.0–30.0% NH_3 basis), potassium sodium tartrate solution ($\text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{KNaO}_6$, BioUltra, 1.5 M in H_2O), potassium tetraiodomercurate(II) solution (Nessler's reagent, for determination of nitrogen solution), were all purchased from Sigma Aldrich. All chemicals were used as received without further purification.

2.2. Synthesis of nanocomposite materials

The metal-heteropolyacids (HPA)- TiO_2 nanocomposites were prepared by the two-step impregnation of TiO_2 . During the first impregnation, a fixed amount of TiO_2 was suspended in the water solution of heteropolyacids (HPA) hydrate (i.e., HPW, HPMo and HSiW). The heteropolyacids weight ratio to TiO_2 of materials varied from 0.1 to 1. After water evaporation and stirring, the resulting sample was dried at 80 °C for 12 h. The obtained HPA- TiO_2 composites were subsequently impregnated with aqueous solutions of relevant metal salts. The target metal content ($M = \text{Pd}$, Cu and Ni) in the final sample was 0.2 wt%. Finally, after a 2 h calcination at 250 °C in static air, the ternary-phased composite of metal-HPA- TiO_2 was obtained. The composites with different metals (i.e., M-HPA- TiO_2) or supports (i.e., ZnO_2 and Al_2O_3), as well as metal-free HPA-support composites, were prepared similarly, simply by replacing either the metal precursor or support. Moreover, a reference Pt- TiO_2 composite was prepared via the strong electrostatic adsorption (SEA) method, with a theoretical Pt loading of 0.2 wt%. Typically, 500 mg TiO_2 was dispersed in water and subjected to sonication treatment. Then, $\text{H}_2\text{PtCl}_6 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ powder was added to the TiO_2 -water suspension under vigorous stirring at room temperature. After 2 h of stirring, the sample precursor was washed with DI water and dried at 80 °C overnight. Lastly, the dried sample was calcined at 250 °C in static air for 2 h. The preparation of Metal-CspW/ TiO_2 requires adding an equimolar amount of CsNO_3 relative to HPW during the first impregnation step.

2.3. Characterization techniques

The X-ray powder diffraction (XRD) patterns of catalysts were collected using the PANalytical Empyrean X-ray diffractometer with a Cu-K α radiation source (40 kV and 30 mA). The ultraviolet–visible diffuse reflectance spectroscopy (UV–vis DRS) analysis was performed on a PerkinElmer Lambda 650S spectrometer, with an integrating sphere covered with BaSO_4 as a reference. The Tauc plots were derived from UV–vis DRS spectra by correlating $(\alpha h\nu)^2$ versus $h\nu$. The scanning

Fig. 1. Schematic illustration of various processes for NH_3 synthesis from N_2 , highlighting their main advantages and limitations.

transmission electron microscopy (STEM) was performed on a TITAN Themis 300 S/TEM microscope equipped with a probe aberration corrector and monochromator, allowing spatial resolution of 70 pm and energy resolution of 150 meV, a super-X windowless 4 quadrant SDD (silicon drift detector) detection system for STEM-EDX mapping and several annual dark field detectors. The measurements were performed with a spot size of about 500 pm, a semi-convergence angle between 20 mrad, and a probe current of approximately 100 pA. For the HAADF images, collection angles were chosen between 50 and 200 mrad. *In-situ* FT-IR spectra were recorded on a Nicolet 6700 FT-IR Spectrometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific) with a mercury cadmium telluride detector. Before the analysis, 40 mg sample was compressed into a wafer with a diameter of 13 mm. Then, the sample wafer was transferred into the *in-situ* reaction cell and degassed under a high vacuum ($< 10^{-5}$ torr) at room temperature for 60 min. Afterward, a mixture of N₂ and CO (or H₂, CO₂) gas (1 bar, 1:9 v/v) was introduced into the reaction cell and maintained in the dark for 30 min, followed by light irradiation and continuous spectral recording. The vapor conditions for FT-IR analysis were established by introducing water vapor into the in situ cell. Pyridine adsorption FT-IR analysis was carried out by introducing 5 torr of pyridine into the in situ reaction cell, followed by vacuum treatment. The concentration of Brønsted acid sites ($\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$) was calculated using an extinction coefficient of the pyridinium band at 1540 cm^{-1} ($\sim 1.36\text{ cm}^2\ \mu\text{mol}^{-1}$). CO adsorption was performed at room temperature on M-HPA/TiO₂ (M = Pt, Pd, Cu, Ni) following 2 pretreatment procedures: (i) evacuation at room temperature for 60 min, and (ii) activation in air at 250 °C for 120 min, followed by cooling to room temperature under vacuum. CO was subsequently dosed at room temperature stepwise up to excess CO, and IR spectra were recorded after equilibration for 10 min for each dose.

The X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) was performed on a SPECS Phoibos 150 photoelectron spectrometer using monochromatic Al K α (1486.7 eV) X-ray irradiation. High-resolution spectra were collected using 300 μm X-ray spot and a pass energy of 20 eV. The binding energy of the photoemission spectra was adjusted to the Ti 2p_{3/2} peak with a binding energy of 458.6 eV.

The analysis of paramagnetic species has been performed by Continuous-Wave Electron Paramagnetic Resonance (CW-EPR). These experiments were performed on a Bruker ELEXSYS E500 spectrometer operating in X-band (9.5 GHz). The EPR spectra were recorded at 100 K to avoid electron-hole recombination. The sample was pretreated in the photocatalytic reactor in CO, then transferred to an EPR quick-pressure tube under an Ar or N₂ atmosphere.

2.4. Photochemical looping and NH₃/NH₄⁺ amount analysis

Photocatalytic light reactions were conducted in a 250 mL batch reactor using a Mercury-Xenon arc lamp (Newport, 200–500 W) as the light source. The optical power density was measured at 279 mW/cm² and maintained consistently throughout the study. In a typical run, 25 mg of catalyst powder was placed into a Teflon cup container inside the reactor. The reactor was evacuated using a vacuum pump and subsequently charged with CO or CO₂ or H₂ and N₂ gases to the desired total pressure (1–10 bar, absolute). To provide water vapor while avoiding direct contact with the catalyst powder, 2 mL of H₂O was added to the bottom of the reactor. All photocatalytic experiments were conducted at ambient temperature: the reactor was cooled at 20 °C using a circulating water bath and monitored with a temperature probe. After the reaction, gaseous products were analyzed using a gas chromatograph (Agilent 8860) equipped with PoraBOND Q and ShinCarbon ST 100/120 columns, a thermal conductivity detector (TCD), and a flame ionization detector (FID) (Figure S1a, SI).

Several techniques were used for analysis of ammonia and ammonium ions. For the analysis of NH₄⁺ produced on the samples, 5 mg of the spent sample powder was directly analyzed using attenuated total reflectance (ATR) on a Nicolet 6700 FT-IR Spectrometer (Thermo Fisher

Scientific) equipped with a mercury cadmium telluride detector. For reference, ammonium phosphotungstic polyoxometalate (NPW) standards were prepared by mixing different ratios of NH₄Cl and HPW, and standard calibration curves for NH₄⁺ quantification were established (Figure S1b, SI).

To release ammonia from ammonium salts in HPW and to quantitatively analyze the produced NH₃, 500 mg of spent sample powder was placed in a tube furnace under an air flow of 5 mL/min at 350 °C for 1 h. The air stream carrying the released ammonium vapor was then bubbled through a 10 vol% H₂SO₄ solution. Subsequently, 0.2 mL of the H₂SO₄ solution containing the absorbed ammonium vapor was mixed with 1 mL of potassium sodium tartrate solution (1.5 M) and 1 mL of Nessler's reagent to quantify the absorbed ammonium. For calibration, various concentrations of NH₄OH solution were added to 1 mL potassium sodium tartrate (1.5 M) and 1 mL Nessler's reagent to build standard curves for NH₄⁺ quantification (Figure S1c, SI).

For the synthesis of concentrated NH₄⁺, a cold trap was used to condense and collect water vapor evaporated from the spent 500 mg sample at 350 °C (Figure S2, SI). By calculating with the standard calibration curve, we obtained the concentration of ammonia in the produced solution is 1.3 wt%. These droplets were collected with 0.4 mL of 10 vol% H₂SO₄ solution and mixed with 0.1 mL of DMSO/D₂O solution (1:2000 v/v; DMSO served as the internal standard) for ¹H nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy analysis (Figure S1d, SI). To further verify the origin of the generated ammonia, ¹⁵N₂ isotope labeling experiments were conducted in the same way that 5 bar ¹⁵N₂ is used to replace 9 bar N₂. The amount of NH₄⁺ in solution was determined to be 1.45 μmol via the ¹H NMR using a pre-established calibration curve. The concentration of ammonia in the absorbing solution was then calculated as: $(\text{Mass of NH}_3) / (\text{Mass of solution}) \times 100\% = (1.45\ \mu\text{mol} \times 18.04\ \text{g/mol}) / (0.002\ \text{g}) \times 100\% \approx 1.3\ \text{wt}\%$. The solution mass is obtained by calculating the difference in cold trap mass before and after the reaction.

Determination of NO₃: Firstly, a certain amount of aqueous catalyst leachate was withdrawn and diluted to 1 mL within the detection range. Then, 1 mL 1 M HCl and 0.01 mL 0.8 wt% sulfamic acid solution were added to the aforementioned solution. The absorption spectrum was measured using an ultraviolet-visible spectrophotometer and the absorption intensities at the wavelength of 220 nm and 275 nm were recorded.

Determination of NO₂: A mixture of p-aminobenzenesulfonamide (4 g), N-(1-Naphthyl) ethylenediamine dihydrochloride (0.2 g), ultra-pure water (50 mL), and phosphoric acid (10 mL, $\rho = 1.70\ \text{g/mL}$) was used as a color reagent. A certain amount of aqueous catalyst leachate was withdrawn and diluted to 1 mL within the detection range. Next, 1 mL color reagent was added into the aforementioned 1 mL solution and mixed uniformly, and the absorption intensity at a wavelength of 540 nm was recorded after 20 min.

Hydrazine determination (N₂H₄): A mixture of ethanol (300 mL), concentrated hydrochloric acid (30 mL), and p-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde (6 g) was used as the color reagent following the Watt and Chrisp method. A certain amount of aqueous catalyst leachate was withdrawn and diluted to 1 mL within the detection range. Subsequently, 1 mL of the color reagent was added to the above solution and mixed thoroughly. After reacting for approximately 10–15 min, the absorbance was recorded at a wavelength of 455 nm using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer.

2.5. Measurement of apparent quantum yield (AQY)

The reaction proceeded within the same batch reactor. 25 mg of catalyst powder was placed into a Teflon cup container inside the reactor. The reactor was evacuated using a vacuum pump and subsequently charged with 1 bar CO and 9 bar N₂. The irradiation time was 60 min. The AQY of the photocatalytic system was determined according to Eq. (9), where NA, I, S and t represent Avogadro's constant, irradiation power density (mW/cm²), irradiation area (cm²) and

irradiation time respectively. During this measurement, a 360 nm band pass filter was used to obtain monochromatic incident light. Therefore, the E_λ which stands for the energy of the incident photon can be calculated according to the following equation, where h and c represent Planck constant and light speed respectively. The AQY in this study was calculated based only on the energy required to generate NH_4^+ from N_2 :

$$\text{AQY} = \frac{n(\text{reacted electrons})}{n(\text{incident photons})} \times 100\% = \frac{n(\text{NH}_4^+) \times 3 \times NA}{I_{\text{st}}/E_\lambda} \times 100\%$$

$$E_\lambda = hc/\lambda$$

2.6. Solid-state NMR measurements

Solid-state ^1H and ^{15}N MAS NMR measurements were performed on a Bruker AVANCE-NEO 18.8 T NMR equipped with a 3.2 mm HXY DVT Bruker MAS probe with 18 kHz rotation speed and working frequencies of 800.13 (^1H) and 81.08 MHz (^{15}N), correspondingly. All the samples were carefully packed into corresponding ZrO_2 MAS rotors under a dry argon atmosphere directly after the described procedures without any contact with oxygen or atmospheric moisture.

For 1D ^1H MAS spectra, the rotor-synchronized DEPTH sequence was used to suppress the background with 32 scans, $3.0 \mu\text{s}$ ^1H 90° -pulse ($\nu_1(^1\text{H}) = 83.3 \text{ kHz}$), 3 s relaxation delay. 1D ^{15}N MAS NMR spectra were obtained by Hahn-echo sequence with 5120 scans, $5.7 \mu\text{s}$ ^{15}N 90° -pulse ($\nu_1(^1\text{H}) = 43.9 \text{ kHz}$), 1 rotor rotation period as a refocusing delay and 5.0 s relaxation. $^{15}\text{N}\{^1\text{H}\}$ CP/MAS spectra were recorded with 20k scans, 1.0 s relaxation delay, 3.0 ms contact time with ramp-shaped 100–70% contact pulse on ^1H -channel. 2D $^{15}\text{N}\{^1\text{H}\}$ CP-HETCOR spectra were recorded with 60 t_1 -increments by 111.1 μs in States-TPPI mode and 1024 scans per each 1D scan. All other parameters were identical to $^{15}\text{N}\{^1\text{H}\}$ CP/MAS experiments. In all MAS NMR experiments, the preliminary presaturation on the excitation channel was used. Bruker Topspin 4.4.0 software was used for data treatment. MestReNova v16 software and the corresponding $^1\text{H}/^{15}\text{N}$ NMR databases were used to attribute the ^{15}N NMR signals.

^{17}O MAS NMR spectra were recorded at $B_0 = 18.8 \text{ T}$ on a Bruker Avance NEO NMR spectrometer with a 3.2 mm HX MAS NMR probe. The operating frequencies of ^1H and ^{17}O were 800.12 and 108.46 MHz, respectively. The spinning speed was 19 or 20 kHz. One pulse sequence (8 μs CT-selective 90° pulse) with the signal enhanced by initially irradiating the satellite transitions (STs) using a ssDFS (Sideband-Selective Double-Frequency-Sweep) [24,25] was used for detection. Up to 100 thousand scans with a 1.5 s recycle delay were recorded. ^{17}O chemical shifts were referenced using water at 0.0 ppm. Before the registration of the NMR spectra, the powder samples were packed in an argon-filled glove box to avoid contact with oxygen or water vapor.

2.7. DFT modelling

Density functional theory (DFT) calculations were performed using VASP [26]. The Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof (PBE) functional [27] and the projector augmented wave (PAW) method [28] were used at the gamma point. A cutoff energy of 500 eV was applied. Electronic and ionic convergence criteria were set to 10^{-5} eV and 0.05 eV/Å, respectively. This ensured adsorption energies converged within about 0.05 eV. All calculations were done at 0 K, without zero-point energy or entropy corrections. The Keggin anion ($\text{PW}_{12}\text{O}_{40}^{3-}$) was placed in a $25 \times 25 \times 25 \text{ \AA}^3$ box to avoid interactions with periodic images. The HPW structure was taken from the Crystallography Open Database, based on Keggin et al. [29]. A Pt single atom catalyst (SAC) was positioned in a quaternary site, bonded to four oxygen atoms, as this configuration was shown to be more favorable than the ternary site [30]. The combined Pt and HPW system (Pt-HPW) included a single oxygen vacancy, resulting in a vacant W atom in the vicinity of Pt. To model proton transfer for N_2 -to-ammonia conversion, all optimizations were performed on

partially hydrogenated Pt-HPW structures, as illustrated in Figure S3, SI.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Synthesis of ammonia and ammonium ions

First, prepared Pt-HPW/ TiO_2 material was exposed to nitrogen under various conditions, with reducing gases such as CO , H_2 , or water vapor. Water was added to the bottom of the batch reactor at room temperature under illumination (Fig. 2a). Analysis of the aqueous phase at the bottom of the reactor using Nessler's reagent or liquid ^1H NMR did not detect free dissolved ammonia under any tested conditions. Ammonium ion formation in the solid sample was confirmed by FTIR spectroscopy, showing a characteristic band at 1418 cm^{-1} corresponding to N–H bending vibration in NH_4^+ [31], and by solid-state ^1H MAS NMR, which revealed two triplet signals around 5 ppm assigned to ammonium ion species with different hydration levels (Fig. 2b-c) [32]. The amount of ammonia was quantified using FTIR spectroscopy (Figure S1b, SI).

Importantly, no NH_4^+ was detected either when nitrogen was used alone or in combination with only water vapor (Fig. 2a). In contrast, the presence of hydrogen led to detectable NH_4^+ formation. When CO was used with N_2 in the absence of water, similar amounts of ammonium ions were produced, along with CO_2 as a side product. CO_2 is produced by the reaction of CO with the oxygen in the material. The structural water present in heteropolyacids serve as a proton source for ammonia formation.

The presence of water enhanced NH_4^+ production, reaching a productivity of $46.1 \mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$, along with nearly stoichiometric amounts of co-produced H_2 and CO_2 . Hydrogen is produced via hydrogen evolution reaction (HER), the water–gas shift (WGS) reaction: $\text{CO} + \text{H}_2\text{O} = \text{CO}_2 + \text{H}_2$ [33], while CO_2 is produced by combining CO oxidation and nitrogen reduction to ammonia: $3\text{CO} + 3\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{N}_2 = 3\text{CO}_2 + 2\text{NH}_3$.

Earlier, we reported that a heteropolyacid–titania composite can convert CO_2 to CO in the presence of water [34]. Interestingly, we found that CO_2 and N_2 can also produce small amounts of ammonia (Fig. 2a), accompanied by the generation of O_2 , CO and H_2 . We infer that CO_2 reacts with Pt-HPW/ TiO_2 to form CO as a mediator, which subsequently promotes ammonia formation. If CO acts as a mediator when CO_2 is used as the source gas, the overall reaction should proceed with the evolution of oxygen, as is usually in photocatalytic synthesis of ammonia: $\text{N}_2 + 3\text{H}_2\text{O} = 2\text{NH}_3 + 3/2\text{O}_2$. The NH_4^+ productivity from CO_2 is approximately one order of magnitude lower than when using CO directly.

Due to the enhanced performance in the presence of CO , we adopted these conditions for further nitrogen reduction studies. The 1418 cm^{-1} FTIR band is attributed to NH_4^+ formed by protonation of ammonia by Brønsted acid sites of the heteropolyacid.

Control experiments using Pt/HPW, Pt/ TiO_2 , and HPW- TiO_2 (Fig. 2d) revealed only trace amounts of produced NH_4^+ . Pd-HPW/ TiO_2 showed performance comparable to the Pt-based system, while the catalysts prepared with other metals, such as Cu and Ni exhibited much lower ammonia productivities. Alternative supports, including HPW/ ZnO , HPW/ Al_2O_3 , HPMo/ TiO_2 , and HSiW/ TiO_2 , also resulted in significantly lower NH_4^+ yields compared to HPW/ TiO_2 (Figure S5, SI), indicating the key role of three components (HPW, TiO_2 and Pt) for the reduction of N_2 to NH_4^+ under the light. It is worth noting that when CsNO_3 is used to replace all hydrogen atoms in HPW (Pt-CSPW/ TiO_2), NH_4^+ formation is completely suppressed, indicating the crucial role of acid sites for stabilization of NH_4^+ cations (Figure S6, SI). Pyridine adsorption studies before and after the reaction using FTIR spectroscopy showed a $\sim 25\%$ decrease in acid site density of heteropolyacid from 384 to 289 $\mu\text{mol/g}$, correlating with the quantity of ammonia converted to NH_4^+ (Figure S4, SI). Time-dependent studies revealed that ammonia production reached a plateau after 18 h, with only a slight increase thereafter (Fig. 2g). This longer duration is necessary to continuously trap the product within the HPW over extended periods and achieve the

Fig. 2. (a) The productivity of NH_4^+ , CO_2 , CO , O_2 and H_2 in different gas conditions on Pt-HPW/TiO₂; (b) FTIR and (c) solid ^1H NMR study of NH_4^+ on NPW, fresh and spent Pt-HPW-TiO₂; (d) The productivity of NH_4^+ , CO_2 and H_2 over different catalysts using CO and N_2 in the presence of water; (e) The productivity of the adsorbed and left NH_4^+ in ten regenerations by air and reaction cycles. (f) ^1H NMR spectra of ammonia produced after desorption from spent Pt-HPW-TiO₂ after reaction with $^{14}\text{N}_2$ and $^{15}\text{N}_2$ with absorption in sulfuric acid solution and (g) Yield of NH_4^+ , CO_2 and H_2 as function of reaction time. General reaction conditions: 25 mg samples (500 mg in e and f), 20 °C, 18 h under light irradiation, 400 W Hg-Xe lamp as the light source. The gaseous condition is N_2 (9 bar) with CO (H_2) (1 bar) or N_2 (1 bar) with CO_2 (9 bar). The water at the bottom of the reactor provides water vapor in (b-g). The metal content of all the above samples is 0.2 wt% and the HPW weight ratio of the sample is 0.4.

high product concentration.

Chemical loop consists of both reaction and regeneration steps. Calcination at 350 °C allows the NH_4^+ ions localized in HPW to be released into NH_3 vapor without destroying the structure of phosphotungstic acid (Figure S7, SI). For regeneration, Pt-HPW/TiO₂ was calcined under an air flow (5 mL/min) at 350 °C for 1 h before the next reaction cycle (Figure S1a, SI). As shown in Fig. 2e, approximately a half of NH_4^+ ions were released as gaseous NH_3 upon calcination which was subsequently absorbed by a 10 vol% H_2SO_4 solution. The highest concentration of ammonia, 1.3 wt%, was achieved using 0.5 g of catalyst. It was confirmed by ^1H NMR analysis through the detection of a triplet at ~6.6 ppm, characteristic of NH_4^+ (Fig. 2f) [35]. The remaining NH_4^+ was retained by the heteropolyacid (See Photochemical looping section for more details of NH_4^+ synthesis experiment). Importantly, Pt-HPW/TiO₂ demonstrated stable performance over ten consecutive regeneration and reaction cycles without significant loss in NH_4^+ productivity (Fig. 2e). To confirm that nitrogen originates from the gaseous nitrogen rather than

from ammonia species initially present in the catalyst, a test with labeled $^{15}\text{N}_2$ was performed. The appearance of a doublet in the ^1H NMR spectrum after adsorption in solution confirms the formation of $^{15}\text{NH}_4^+$ species (Fig. 2f) [36].

Furthermore, we evaluated influence of catalyst composition and operating parameters on ammonia synthesis. Ammonia yield decreases with decreasing N_2 partial pressure when CO is used as the reactant. However, when CO_2 , a less reactive compound, is used, ammonia formation increases at higher CO_2 pressures, which correlates with the partial pressure of CO in the reactor (Figure S8a, SI). The increase in the content of HPW leads to a slight increase in the production of NH_4^+ , reaching a maximum when HPW/TiO₂ weight ratio is 0.4 (Figure S8b, SI). The Pt content has a weak effect on NH_4^+ production. Even trace amounts of Pt (0.05 wt%) result in comparable NH_4^+ production to that achieved with higher Pt loadings. It is interesting to note that at a Pt content higher than 0.2 wt%, NH_4^+ production decreases most probably due to the formation of Pt metallic nanoparticles (Figure S8c, SI).

3.2. Characterization of the material

The X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns of the various samples are shown in Fig. 3a. Both Pt-HPW/TiO₂ and HPW/TiO₂ exhibit patterns of mixed crystalline phases of TiO₂ (anatase and rutile) along with the reflections corresponding to Keggin-type HPW hydrate (PDF#50-0657). The increased full width at half maximum (FWHM) of the HPW-related peaks in both Pt-HPW/TiO₂ and HPW/TiO₂ suggests partial disordering of the HPW polyhedra, likely due to calcination, which facilitates anchoring and dispersion of HPW fragments on the TiO₂ surface [37]. Indeed, STEM images of the most active Pt-HPW/TiO₂ sample, before the reaction, after the reaction, and after the regeneration (Fig. 3b–c, Figures S9–S11, SI) demonstrate a high dispersion of HPW species on the

TiO₂ support. Importantly, no leaching or agglomeration of Pt or HPW over TiO₂ was observed following the reaction and regeneration steps. These findings, consistent with the XRD results, indicate that intermediate calcination is essential to disperse and stabilize HPW fragments on the TiO₂ surface.

The UV–visible spectra of the samples are shown in Fig. 3d. All samples exhibit strong absorption in the ultraviolet region (<400 nm), characteristic of both HPW and TiO₂. [38] When we filtered out all light except ultraviolet (Figure S12, SI), it had almost no effect on the productivity. To match this feature, we used a Newport Mercury-Xenon Arc Lamp (Model: 66142), with UV enhancement characteristics compared with a normal Xe Arc lamp. Interestingly, Tauc's plot analysis (Figure S13, SI) reveals that the incorporation of Pt and HPW into TiO₂

Fig. 3. (a) XRD patterns of different samples; (b) HAADF-STEM and corresponding EDS-mapping images of Pt-HPW/TiO₂; (c) High-resolution HAADF-STEM image of Pt-HPW/TiO₂; (d) UV-Vis DRS spectra of different samples; (e) IR spectra of temperature-programmed CO desorption over Pt-HPW/TiO₂ under light irradiation; (f) XPS analysis W 4f of NPW, fresh Pt-HPW/TiO₂, Pt-HPW/TiO₂ after reaction with CO or CO+N₂, and Pt-HPW-TiO₂ after regeneration.

reduces the bandgap energy. Pure TiO₂ displays a bandgap of approximately 3.26 eV, while Pt-HPW/TiO₂ shows a narrowed bandgap of ~3.05 eV [39].

To evaluate the Pt dispersion, FTIR CO (Fig. 3e) adsorption measurements were performed on the Pt-HPW/TiO₂ catalyst. A small CO adsorption peak was observed under dark conditions at 2190 cm⁻¹, indicating that Pt in the material is present as cationic species [40]. However, under light irradiation, a narrow peak appears at 2143 cm⁻¹, which is typically attributed to CO adsorbed on Pt single atoms on an electron-deficient surface such as heteropolyacid [41]. Evacuation under the temperature from 25 °C to 300 °C under vacuum leads to the gradual desorption of CO from the catalyst, without any shift in the band position. This indicates the absence of dipole-dipole interactions between adsorbed CO molecules and confirms the atomic dispersion of the primary Pt species on the catalyst [42]. To elucidate the effect of the metal on ammonia synthesis, FTIR CO adsorption experiments were performed over other catalysts (Figure S14, SI). The results demonstrate strong CO adsorption on Pd-HPW/TiO₂, with a band at 1964 cm⁻¹ that can be assigned to bridged carbonyls over Pd⁰ sites [43]. This also suggests that, unlike Pt, Pd is present in the catalysts in the form of metallic nanoparticles. In contrast, CO adsorption on Cu- and

Ni-containing catalysts produced bands at 2135 and 2194 cm⁻¹, respectively, which are attributed to CO coordinated to cationic Cu⁺ and Ni²⁺ species [44,45]. This suggests difficulty in reducing these metals to their metallic states. Collectively, these results indicate that Pd and Pt readily form metallic sites capable of strong CO binding, whereas Cu and Ni predominantly remain in cationic forms, implying weaker reducibility and a greater tendency to maintain oxidized surfaces.

XPS analysis was used to study the material before and after the reaction. As shown in Fig. 3f, in both NPW and fresh Pt-HPW/TiO₂ the W 4f spectrum displays a main doublet peak attributed to W 4f_{7/2} and W 4f_{5/2} with a doublet separation of 2.18 eV and a W 4f_{7/2} BE at 37.4 ± 0.1 eV, corresponding to W⁶⁺ [46]. A small intensity doublet peak with W 4f_{7/2} BE at 34.5 eV is also detected and is attributed to W⁵⁺ species. When only pure CO is added, the spectrum exhibits an increase in the W⁵⁺ contribution, reaching approximately 15%. This increase is attributed to the partial reduction of HPW by CO, leading to oxygen removal and possibly oxygen vacancies. When N₂ is added together with CO, the W⁵⁺ contribution after the reaction decreases to approximately 8%. Upon regeneration under O₂, the W⁵⁺ ratio returns to its initial value, consistent with reoxidation of the W⁵⁺ tungsten centers.

Fig. 4. (a) Subsequent treatment of Pt-HPW/TiO₂ under light irradiation by CO with N₂ and then by added water vapor. (b) In situ FT-IR spectra of Pt-HPW/TiO₂ exposed to N₂ with CO under light irradiation. (c) EPR spectra at 100 K of samples treated under light for 18 h under 1 bar CO (blue), briefly flashed under 9 bar N₂ (red), and CO-reduced then air-reoxidized (black). (d) 1D ¹⁵N MAS and ¹⁵N{¹H} CP/MAS NMR spectra of Pt-HPW/TiO₂ reacted with 5 bar ¹⁵N₂ and 1 bar CO in (1) 1 h, (2) 18 h and (3) pure ¹⁵NH₄PW. (e) 2D ¹⁵N{¹H} CP-HETCOR NMR spectra of Pt-HPW/TiO₂ reacted with ¹⁵N₂ and CO in 1 h. General reaction conditions: 25 mg samples, 20 °C, 18 h under light irradiation, 400 W Hg-Xe lamp as the light source. The gaseous condition is N₂ (9 bar) and CO (1 bar). The water at the bottom of the reactor provides water vapor in (a). The metal content of all the above samples is 0.2 wt% and the HPW weight ratio of the sample is 0.4.

3.3. Mechanism of the reaction

To clarify the role of CO and water in N_2 activation and reduction, each reaction step has been investigated. The Pt-HPW/TiO₂ catalyst was first treated in the dry state with CO and N₂ (Fig. 4a). The results demonstrate that CO treatment leads to the reduction of HPW leading to oxygen vacancies, accompanied by CO₂ generation. The sample develops a dark blue color, indicating an increase in the W⁵⁺ contribution, as confirmed by XPS analysis. No N₂ conversion is observed without HPW partial reduction by CO (Fig. 2a). This suggests that N₂ activation occurs through its interaction with reduced H₃PW₁₂O₄₀ (Fig. 5).

In the presence of water, the reaction proceeds further, resulting in a higher yield of ammonium and a less intense blue coloration (Fig. 4a). This behavior is attributed to the facilitated hydrolysis of reduced nitrogen species located in oxygen vacancies. The resulting ammonia is subsequently stabilized as protonated ammonium species on the acidic sites of the heteropolyacid.

When CO₂ and water vapor were used as the reactant gas, only small amounts of H₂, O₂, and CO were detected. Upon adding N₂ into the reactor, the formation of ammonia was observed. These results demonstrate that CO₂ can be converted into the reaction intermediate CO, which subsequently participates in ammonia formation (Figure S15, SI).

To confirm this mechanism, a combination of in situ techniques was employed, including FTIR, solid-state NMR, and EPR. In particular, in situ FTIR spectroscopy was used to study surface species on Pt-HPW/TiO₂ under simulated reaction conditions (Fig. 4b). Under dark conditions and in the presence of only CO and N₂, a bending vibration band of structural water is observed at 1618 cm⁻¹. Upon illumination, a peak appears at 2308 cm⁻¹, attributed to the antisymmetric stretching vibration of CO₂ [47]. CO₂ is likely produced by the reaction of CO with mobile oxygen species from H₃PW₁₂O₄₀. A band at 1418 cm⁻¹, typically associated with ammonium salts of HPW, appears rapidly under light exposure and increases gradually over time. [31] Subsequently, a band at 1495 cm⁻¹ emerges, which is likely related to NH₄⁺ ions interacting

with the reduced heteropolyacid. This process is accompanied by the appearance of a broad shoulder at around 1700 cm⁻¹, which is unusually high for the bending vibration of water and is likely due to perturbed structural water interacting with the reduced heteropolyacid [48–50]. Time-resolved FTIR spectra confirm these assignments, showing a coherent increase in the intensities of bands attributed to NH₄⁺ and water associated with the reduced heteropolyacid. Interestingly, FTIR analysis during N₂ conversion in the presence of CO and water vapor (Figure S16, SI) shows a significant decrease in the 1495 cm⁻¹ band intensity, indicating competition between ammonia and water adsorption at oxygen vacancies. To exclude the possibility that the 1700 cm⁻¹ band originates from carbonyl compounds, a control experiment was conducted in the presence of H₂ and N₂ but without the addition of CO and CO₂. Similar bands were observed, supporting the assignment of the band at 1700 cm⁻¹ to structural water rather than to carbonyl species (Figure S17, SI). In situ FTIR spectroscopy of CO₂ with N₂ exhibited similar characteristic vibrational bands, with additional strong bands at 1537 and 1487 cm⁻¹, which can be assigned to the asymmetric and symmetric stretches of carbonates [51] formed from adsorbed CO₂ (Figure S18, SI).

To further validate the role of oxygen vacancies in nitrogen activation, we conducted EPR experiments (Fig. 4c). An intense signal centered around $g \approx 1.998$ – 1.938 was observed after treatment of Pt-HPW/TiO₂ under CO, which is attributed to Ti³⁺ species, characteristic of paramagnetic centers in the titania matrix. [52] A broader signal at $g \approx 1.795$ is assigned to W⁵⁺ species, indicating partial reduction of W⁶⁺ under these conditions by CO, accompanied by the generation of oxygen vacancies [53]. The intensity of this signal significantly decreased (30%) in the presence of N₂, which could be attributed to the N₂ reduction by HPW involving W⁵⁺ species and oxygen vacancies. As some oxygen vacancies are EPR-silent (diamagnetic) and electrons may delocalize between W and vacancy sites, the W⁵⁺ signal provides a qualitative, relative measure of vacancy generation and consumption rather than a direct quantification.

This signal disappears after subsequent treatment in air, suggesting

Fig. 5. (a) Schematic illustration of the mechanism of the reaction (b) Relative stabilities of dissociated NH_x-NH_x intermediates on the partially hydrogenated Pt-HPW catalyst. Energies are provided in eV and (c) Ball-and-stick representations of the initial state, transition state, and final state involved in NH₂NH₂ dissociation on Pt-HPW. Key bond distances characterizing the transition state are reported in Å. Reaction energies (ΔE) and activation barriers (E_a) are provided in eV.

that W^{5+} is fully reoxidized to W^{6+} under oxidizing conditions. Interestingly, we found that H_2 generates only trace amounts of oxygen vacancies capable of reacting with N_2 in comparison with CO. This can be explained by the fact that CO reduces the lattice oxygen of the heteropolyacid directly, whereas H_2 activates oxygen much more slowly via dissociation and spillover on the heteropolyacid surface [54]. In contrast, CO_2 partially converted to CO under the reaction conditions, generates a large number of oxygen vacancies that can readily interact with N_2 (Figure S19, SI). The low partial pressure of CO derived from CO_2 is insufficient to supply enough hydrogen for some ammonia production. In the presence of CO_2 , the catalyst also exhibits high stability and ammonia selectivity (Figure S20, SI).

As shown in Fig. 4d, the ^{15}N solid-state NMR spectrum recorded after 1 h of exposure to CO and $^{15}N_2$ under irradiation reveals a series of distinct signals. Sharp peaks at 17.3 and 20.2 ppm, along with a broad shoulder centered at around 27 ppm, are observed. Based on their chemical shifts, these signals correspond to $^{15}NH_4^+$ ions, which typically appear between 17–35 ppm depending on their local chemical environment and hydrogen bonding interactions [55]. A reference $^{15}NH_4PW$ sample, prepared using $^{15}NH_4Cl$, shows two narrow signals at 17.2 and 17.7 ppm, previously assigned to bulk and surface ammonium ions, respectively. Therefore, the 17.3 ppm signal in our system can be attributed to NH_4^+ ions associated with the original hydrated heteropolyacid structure. Since the PW species are partially reduced during the reaction, only a minor amount of undisturbed NH_4PW is detected.

The 17.3 ppm signal exhibits higher intensity in the CP-MAS spectrum, indicating strong hydrogen bonding and a higher degree of water coordination. The appearance of the 20.2 ppm signal in the early stages of the reaction likely originates from NH_4^+ species located near or within oxygen-deficient regions of the material [56]. The broad signal at 27 ppm may be attributed to partially dehydrogenated ammonia species NH_x adsorbed over the reduced HPW framework. This assignment was confirmed by two-dimensional 1H - ^{15}N CP-HETCOR NMR spectra (Fig. 4e), which provide further insight into the nitrogen environments. The ^{15}N resonance at 17.3 ppm correlates with a 1H signal at 5 ppm, consistent with ammonium species in fully hydrated, non-reduced HPW. In contrast, the 20.2 ppm ^{15}N signal correlates with broader 1H signals at ~3 and 6–7 ppm, suggesting asymmetric localization of NH_4^+ . These correlations indicate the interactions between NH_4^+ and both adsorbed water (6–7 ppm) and non-acidic OH groups (3 ppm) formed on partially reduced HPW. A broad component at ~10–30 ppm in the 1H dimension (orange and green areas in Fig. 4e) correlates with the 3 and 4 ppm 1H signal; however, it does not correlate with the water signal at 6–7 ppm, and, most likely, correspond to non-protonated primary (- NH_2) and secondary (-NH-) species on dehydrated partially reduced and, therefore, disturbed PW ions.

Upon addition of water and subsequent hydrolysis, all broad ^{15}N signals disappear in the 1D spectra. Only sharp signals remain at 17.3, 20.9, and 22.0 ppm, which can be attributed exclusively to NH_4^+ ions compensating the charge of HPW anions in various structural states, including partially reduced or hydrated forms. This observation further supports the spectral assignments.

Extending the reaction time from 1 to 18 h results in a progressive shift of the main NH_4^+ signal to 22 ppm. This is attributed to increased consumption of coordinated water. Consequently, the 17.3 ppm signal becomes more pronounced in the CP/MAS spectrum after 18 h, compared to after 1 h. Under extended reaction conditions in the presence of CO and N_2 , and in the absence of sufficient water, the amount of unsaturated N species increases. These species lack proximate protons and exhibit broad ^{15}N signal at ~30 ppm in the direct-polarization MAS NMR spectrum. Notably, this signal is absent in the $^{15}N\{^1H\}$ CP/MAS spectrum, confirming the low proton proximity. Upon water addition, these tertiary amine species hydrolyze completely into NH_4^+ ions, which appear as a sharp signal at 22 ppm, compensating for the charge of highly disturbed, partially reduced PW anions. The presence of CO_2 and water leads to the direct formation of hydrolyzed NH_4^+ ions, as observed

in the narrow signals at 18 and 21 ppm in the $^{15}N\{^1H\}$ MAS and CP/MAS spectra (Figure S21, SI).

Characteristic signals at ~75 and ~80 ppm after 1 h of test in CO, which disappear after 18 h, indicate the presence of intermediate species related to the reaction mechanism. These signals are attributed to secondary (-NH-) and tertiary (-N=) nitrogen atoms within hydrazine-like (N-NH) surface fragments [57]. The assignment is further supported by the absence of the 80 ppm signal in $^{15}N\{^1H\}$ -CP/MAS spectra, indicating low proton proximity, while the 75 ppm signal remains visible, consistent with a protonated secondary nitrogen. This suggests that only intermediates stabilized by a lack of proton donors, such as coordinated water, are observed. In contrast, the presence of protons of water promotes rapid hydrolysis of these intermediates, as confirmed by the spectra of the hydrolyzed sample.

According to the literature, two possible pathways have been proposed: direct N_2 scission and “hydrogen-assisted” cleavage after partial hydrogenation to NH_x-NH_y (x and $y = 0-2$) species [4]. The mechanism of nitrogen fixation in our system is governed by a photochemical looping cycle in which the interaction between CO, N_2 , water vapor, and the Pt-HPW/ TiO_2 catalyst enables selective and regenerative NH_4^+ formation under mild conditions (Fig. 5a). Initially, CO plays the role of a reductant, generating oxygen vacancies. CO can be produced from CO_2 by photocatalytic reduction: electrons reduce CO_2 to CO, while holes oxidize water to generate protons and oxygen. CO partially reduces the heteropolyacid (HPW), forming W^{5+} species and oxygen vacancies, as evidenced by XPS and EPR analyses. These vacancies act as high-affinity sites for N_2 adsorption and activation, facilitated by back-donation from W^{5+} centers into the orbitals of N_2 . Under illumination, electrons from TiO_2 conduction band are transferred to HPW, enhancing its reduction. Single-atom Pt facilitates CO oxidation and contributes to the generation of oxygen vacancies, while also stabilizing electron-rich sites necessary for N_2 activation [58,59]. Once N_2 is adsorbed and activated at these reduced HPW sites, protons from water and the Brønsted acid sites of HPW participate in a proton-coupled electron transfer, forming ammonia through hydrazine-type (NH_2-NH_2) intermediates, as supported by DFT calculations and ^{15}N NMR spectroscopy. After optimizing these dissociated intermediates (“ NH_x-NH_y ”), our DFT calculations revealed that adsorbed NH_2-NH_2 is by far the most stable intermediate (Fig. 5b, Table S2, SI). This suggests that N_2 conversion to ammonia proceeds mainly through the NH_x-NH_y (hydrazine) pathway.

The lack of protons during the dry test can lead to partially hydrogenated hydrazine species and nitrogen, as observed by NMR, and a slower reaction rate. Upon addition of water, the rapid conversion to ammonium ions indicates that hydrogen-saturated species are the most favorable for the reaction. The protons can also be supplied during the abstraction of oxygen from water by reaction with CO (Fig. 5a). The cleavage of NH_2-NH_2 into two NH_2 fragments according to DFT modelling proceeds with a reaction energy of -1.79 eV and an activation energy of 0.21 eV (Fig. 5c). These results indicate that this step is both thermodynamically and kinetically favorable. Ammonia is then protonated and trapped in the solid as NH_4^+ on HPW Brønsted sites, leading to the formation of a stable ammonium phosphotungstate. The regeneration step is driven by water, which refills the oxygen vacancies, and completing the catalytic cycle. Importantly, water is essential not only for supplying protons but also for maintaining catalyst activity via vacancy regeneration. Without water, nitrogen reduction stalls and reduced species accumulate, as observed by NMR and FTIR. This pathway was investigated using ^{17}O solid-state NMR spectroscopy of the Pt-HPW/ TiO_2 sample after reaction with $H_2^{17}O$ placed at the bottom of the reactor (Figure S22, SI). The ^{17}O MAS NMR spectrum of the catalyst shows three intense signals at ca. 770, 430, and 410 ppm, assigned to terminal oxo (W=O) and two inequivalent bridging oxygens (W-O-W) of the Keggin anion, respectively [Kozhevnikov, I.V., Sinnema, A., Jansen, R.J.J. et al. ^{17}O NMR determination of proton sites in solid heteropoly acid $H_3PW_{12}O_{40}$. ^{31}P , ^{29}Si and ^{17}O NMR, FT-IR and XRD study of $H_3PW_{12}O_{40}$ and $H_4SiW_{12}O_{40}$ supported on carbon. *Catal Lett* 27,

187–197 (1994). <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00806992>. Oxygen in TiO₂ appears as two weak signals at 596 and 560 ppm, indicating efficient oxygen exchange into the HPW framework. This is fully consistent with HPW acting as a dynamic oxygen reservoir in comparison with TiO₂ under photocatalytic and redox conditions, particularly in the presence of Pt.

CO is an expensive reducing agent, and our results demonstrate that CO₂ can be used instead to generate CO via reduction over HPW. According to the proposed mechanism, the generated CO subsequently promotes ammonia synthesis, being oxidized back to CO₂ in the process. However, the low partial pressure of CO in this case results in significantly less efficient ammonia formation. Compared to conventional photocatalytic nitrogen fixation approaches, which typically suffer from low ammonia concentrations, poor selectivity, and challenging product separation in aqueous media, our photochemical looping strategy offers several critical advancements. Notably, the solid-state trapping of ammonia as a stable ammonium salt allows for direct product capture and simplifies downstream handling.

The system achieves an exceptionally high NH₄⁺ concentration (1.3 wt%), far exceeding most reported values (see Table S1, SI), while maintaining > 99% ammonia selectivity and no any other side product in gas and surface (Figure S23, SI), a benchmark rarely reached in liquid-phase photocatalysis. Under the optimized reaction condition of Pt-HPW/TiO₂, an apparent quantum yield (AQY) of 0.73% was achieved under the irradiation of 360 nm monochromatic light, which highlights the challenge of photocatalytic N₂ reduction.

Unlike many systems relying on doped semiconductors, noble-metal-loaded oxides, or metal–organic frameworks, our approach uses a bifunctional single-atom Pt-HPW/TiO₂ composite that integrates redox-active W sites, Brønsted acidity, and photogenerated charge separation within a chemically regenerable framework [60–64]. Oxygen vacancies generated by CO are shown to play a decisive role in N₂ activation [65], and in comparison with other materials such as BiOCl or In₂O₃ [11,15], the vacancies here are part of a regenerable loop, sustained by water as both a proton and oxygen donor. This vacancy–refilling strategy, enabled by HPW's redox flexibility, is distinct from static defect sites in traditional photocatalysts and leads to enhanced durability across multiple regeneration cycles without loss of activity.

Altogether, this work introduces a modular and cyclic platform that addresses key bottlenecks in photocatalytic N₂ reduction, activation, selectivity, and separation, by coupling molecular catalysis with solid-state engineering, representing a significant step toward scalable, sustainable nitrogen fixation. Although the energy efficiency of this reaction remains low, the concept of photocatalytic production of solid ammonia could see widespread use in the future. Different methods, including chemical and biological ammonia removal, could potentially be employed for this process.

4. Conclusion

In this work, we demonstrate a photochemical looping strategy for nitrogen fixation under mild conditions, enabling the synthesis of solid ammonium salts using a Pt-HPW/TiO₂ photocatalyst, with either CO or CO derived from CO₂ as the reductant, and water vapor as a proton and oxygen source. This approach effectively overcomes key limitations of conventional photocatalytic N₂ fixation and leads to concentrated ammonia solutions.

Mechanistic studies reveal that CO reduces the heteropolyacid, generating W⁵⁺ centers and oxygen vacancies that serve as active sites for N₂ activation and reduction. Water plays a dual role in proton transfer and vacancy regeneration, enabling sustained cycling of the system. The formation of stable ammonium phosphotungstate allows for efficient NH₃ capture and recovery, with solution concentrations up to 1.3 wt%, surpassing many reported photocatalytic systems.

This work establishes a scalable, cyclic, and selective strategy for light-driven nitrogen fixation using abundant molecules, opening

avenues for solid-state ammonia harvesting based on molecular catalyst architectures.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Yinghao Wang: Writing - original draft, Methodology, Investigation. **Geqian Fang:** Investigation, Validation. **Feixiang Shen:** Investigation. **Olena Vovk:** Investigation, Data curation and Visualization. **Karima Ben Tayeb:** Investigation, Validation and Visualization. **Maya Marinova:** Investigation, Data curation and Visualization. **Marc Bria:** Investigation and Data curation. **Teddy Roy:** Investigation. **Mariya Shamzhy:** Data curation, Formal analysis. **Pardis Simon:** Investigation, Data curation, Validation and Visualization. **Yury G. Kolyagin:** Investigation, Data curation, Validation, Visualization, Methodology and Writing- Reviewing and Editing. **Jeremie Zaffrane:** Investigation, Visualization, Methodology and Writing- Reviewing and Editing. **Andrei Khodakov:** Writing- Reviewing and Editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Vitaly V. Ordonsky:** Conceptualization, Writing- Reviewing and Editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supporting Information

Experimental schematic; Standard curve for products' quantification; The ammonium production; Regeneration; TPD-MS spectra; HAADF-STEM images materials; The optimization of the reaction of ammonium synthesis; In-situ FTIR analysis of reaction and Py adsorption; Comparison with the literature. DFT calculation model and information.

Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.apcatb.2026.126633](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apcatb.2026.126633).

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- [1] X.H. Wang, B. Wu, Y. Zhu, D. Wang, N.B. Li, Z.J. Xu, H.Q. Luo, Design refinement of catalytic system for scale-up mild nitrogen photo-fixation, *Nano-Micro Lett.* 17 (2025) 182.
- [2] H. Cheng, P. Cui, F. Wang, L.-X. Ding, H. Wang, High efficiency electrochemical nitrogen fixation achieved with a lower pressure reaction system by changing the chemical equilibrium, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 58 (2019) 15541–15547.
- [3] J. Xiong, P. Song, J. Di, H. Li, Atomic-level active sites steering in ultrathin photocatalysts to trigger high efficiency nitrogen fixation, *Chem. Eng. J.* 402 (2020) 126208.
- [4] S.L. Foster, S.I.P. Bakovic, R.D. Duda, S. Maheshwari, R.D. Milton, S.D. Minter, M. J. Janik, J.N. Renner, L.F. Greenlee, Catalysts for nitrogen reduction to ammonia, *Nat. Catal.* 1 (2018) 490–500.
- [5] K.H.R. Rouwenhorst, A.G.J. Van der Ham, L. Lefferts, Beyond Haber-Bosch: the renaissance of the clauder process, *Int. J. Hydrog. Energy* 46 (2021) 21566–21579.
- [6] T. Kandemir, M.E. Schuster, A. Senyshyn, M. Behrens, R. Schlögl, The Haber-Bosch process revisited: on the real structure and stability of “ammonia iron” under working conditions, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 52 (2013) 12723–12726.
- [7] J. Li, G. Zhan, J. Yang, F. Quan, C. Mao, Y. Liu, B. Wang, F. Lei, L. Li, A.W.M. Chan, L. Xu, Y. Shi, Y. Du, W. Hao, P.K. Wong, J. Wang, S.-X. Dou, L. Zhang, J.C. Yu, Efficient ammonia electrosynthesis from nitrate on strained Ruthenium nanoclusters, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 142 (2020) 7036–7046.
- [8] A.J. Medford, M.C. Hatzell, Photon-driven nitrogen fixation: current progress, thermodynamic considerations, and future outlook, *ACS Catal.* 7 (2017) 2624–2643.
- [9] W. Wang, H. Zhang, S. Zhang, Y. Liu, G. Wang, C. Sun, H. Zhao, Potassium-ion-assisted regeneration of active cyano groups in carbon nitride nanoribbons: visible-light-driven photocatalytic nitrogen reduction, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 58 (2019) 16644–16650.
- [10] Z. Li, Z. Gao, B. Li, L. Zhang, R. Fu, Y. Li, X. Mu, L. Li, Fe-Pt nanoclusters modified Mott-Schottky photocatalysts for enhanced ammonia synthesis at ambient conditions, *Appl. Catal. B* 262 (2020) 118276.
- [11] P. Li, Y. Gao, A.G.L. Borthwick, P. Li, H. Zhang, F. Chen, L. Chen, F. Li, W. Liu, Photocatalytic nitrogen reduction for ammonia synthesis accelerated by overcoming photo-dember effect, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 64 (2025) e202503097.
- [12] S. Wu, C. He, L. Wang, J. Zhang, High-efficiency electron tandem flow mode on carbon nitride/titanium dioxide heterojunction for visible light nitrogen photofixation, *Chem. Eng. J.* 443 (2022) 136425.
- [13] M. Mohebinia, C. Wu, G. Yang, S. Dai, A. Hakimian, T. Tong, H. Ghasemi, Z. Wang, D. Wang, Z. Ren, J. Bao, Ultrathin bismuth oxyiodide nanosheets for photocatalytic ammonia generation from nitrogen and water under visible to near-infrared light, *Mater. Today Phys.* 16 (2021) 100293.
- [14] S. Zhang, Y. Zhao, R. Shi, C. Zhou, G.I.N. Waterhouse, L.-Z. Wu, C.-H. Tung, T. Zhang, Efficient photocatalytic nitrogen fixation over Cu^{δ+}-modified defective ZnAl-layered double hydroxide nanosheets, *Adv. Energy Mater.* 10 (2020) 1901973.
- [15] H. Xu, Y. Wang, X. Dong, N. Zheng, H. Ma, X. Zhang, Fabrication of In₂O₃/In₂S₃ microsphere heterostructures for efficient and stable photocatalytic nitrogen fixation, *Appl. Catal. B* 257 (2019) 117932.
- [16] J. Di, J. Xia, M.F. Chisholm, J. Zhong, C. Chen, X. Cao, F. Dong, Z. Chi, H. Chen, Y.-X. Wang, J. Xiong, S.-Z. Yang, H. Li, Z. Liu, S. Dai, Defect-tailoring mediated electron-hole separation in single-unit-cell Bi₃O₄Br nanosheets for boosting photocatalytic hydrogen evolution and nitrogen fixation, *Adv. Mater.* 31 (2019) 1807576.
- [17] S.S. Lam, V.-H. Nguyen, M.T. Nguyen Dinh, D.Q. Khieu, D.D. La, H.T. Nguyen, D.V. N. Vo, C. Xia, R.S. Varma, M. Shokouhimehr, C.C. Nguyen, Q.V. Le, W. Peng, Mainstream avenues for boosting graphitic carbon nitride efficiency: towards enhanced solar light-driven photocatalytic hydrogen production and environmental remediation, *J. Mater. Chem. A* 8 (2020) 10571–10603.
- [18] J. Zhao, G. Ren, X. Meng, Recent advances on MOFs for photocatalytic and electrocatalytic nitrogen reduction to produce ammonia, *Nano Energy* 130 (2024) 110109.
- [19] S. Ghoshal, A. Ghosh, P. Roy, B. Ball, A. Pramanik, P. Sarkar, Recent progress in computational design of single-atom/cluster catalysts for electrochemical and solar-driven N₂ Fixation, *ACS Catal.* 12 (2022) 15541–15575.
- [20] Z. Xia, L. Lin, X. Chen, J. Zhai, C. Xue, S. Jia, J. Jiao, M. Dong, W. Han, X. Zheng, T. Deng, X. Zou, C. Xian, H. Wu, B. Han, Solar-driven upcycling of polylactic acid to alanine over Pt/Cds–TiO₂ heterojunction single-atom photocatalyst, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 147 (2025) 45357–45365.
- [21] J.A. Delgado, C. Claver, S. Castillón, D. Curulla-Ferré, V.V. Ordomsky, C. Godard, Fischer-Tropsch synthesis catalysed by small TiO₂ supported cobalt nanoparticles prepared by sodium borohydride reduction, *Appl. Catal. A Gen.* 513 (2016) 39–46.
- [22] J. Prech, D.R. Strossi Pedrollo, N.R. Marcilio, B. Gu, A.S. Peregodova, M. Mazur, V. V. Ordomsky, V. Valtchev, A.Y. Khodakov, Core-Shell metal zeolite composite catalysts for in situ processing of Fischer-Tropsch hydrocarbons to gasoline type fuels, *ACS, Catalysis* 10 (2020) 2544–2555.
- [23] Z. Lian, D. Luo, J. Yang, Y. Yang, S. Tang, H. Li, D. Zhang, H. Li, Spatial decoupling of adsorption and transformation sites on Ag-Cu dual-single-atom catalysts for highly selective photocatalytic nitrate-to-ammonia reduction, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 65 (2026) e202516964.
- [24] M. Goswami, P.J.Mv Bentum, A.P.M. Kentgens, Sensitivity enhancement in MAS NMR of half-integer quadrupolar nuclei using sideband selective double-frequency sweeps, *Can. J. Chem.* 89 (2011) 1130–1137.
- [25] Q. Wang, J. Trébosc, Y. Li, O. Lafon, S. Xin, J. Xu, B. Hu, N. Feng, J.-P. Amoureux, F. Deng, Uniform signal enhancement in MAS NMR of half-integer quadrupolar nuclei using quadruple-frequency sweeps, *J. Magn. Reson.* 293 (2018) 92–103.
- [26] J. Hafner, Ab-initio simulations of materials using VASP: density-functional theory and beyond, *J. Comput. Chem.* 29 (2008) 2044–2078.
- [27] J.P. Perdew, K. Burke, M. Ernzerhof, Generalized gradient approximation made simple, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 77 (1996) 3865–3868.
- [28] G. Kresse, D. Joubert, From ultrasoft pseudopotentials to the projector augmented-wave method, *Phys. Rev. B* 59 (1999) 1758–1775.
- [29] J.F. Keggin, W.L. Bragg, The structure and formula of 12-phosphotungstic acid, *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London, Series A Contain. Pap. a Math. Phys. Character* 144 (1934) 75–100.
- [30] C. Dong, M. Marinova, K.B. Tayeb, O.V. Safonova, Y. Zhou, D. Hu, S. Chernyak, M. Corda, J. Zaffran, A.Y. Khodakov, V.V. Ordomsky, Direct photocatalytic synthesis of acetic acid from methane and CO at ambient temperature using water as oxidant, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 145 (2023) 1185–1193.
- [31] B. Zhang, H. Asakura, N. Yan, Atomically dispersed Rhodium on self-assembled phosphotungstic acid: structural features and catalytic CO oxidation properties, *Ind. & Eng. Chem. Res.* 56 (2017) 3578–3587.
- [32] T. Le Marchand, T. Schubeis, M. Bonaccorsi, P. Paluch, D. Lalli, A.J. Pell, L. B. Andreas, K. Jaudzems, J. Stanek, G. Pintacuda, 1H-detected biomolecular NMR under fast magic-angle spinning, *Chem. Rev.* 122 (2022) 9943–10018.
- [33] D.B. Pal, R. Chand, S.N. Upadhyay, P.K. Mishra, Performance of water gas shift reaction catalysts: a review, *Renew. Sust. Energy Rev.* 93 (2018) 549–565.
- [34] X. Yu, S. Moldovan, V.V. Ordomsky, A.Y. Khodakov, Design of core-shell titania-heteropolyacid-metal nanocomposites for photocatalytic reduction of CO₂ to CO at ambient temperature, *Nanoscale Adv.* 1 (2019) 4321–4330.
- [35] Y. Guan, H. Wen, K. Cui, Q. Wang, W. Gao, Y. Cai, Z. Cheng, Q. Pei, Z. Li, H. Cao, T. He, J. Guo, P. Chen, Light-driven ammonia synthesis under mild conditions using lithium hydride, *Nat. Chem.* 16 (2024) 373–379.
- [36] P. Xia, X. Pan, S. Jiang, J. Yu, B. He, P.M. Ismail, W. Bai, J. Yang, L. Yang, H. Zhang, M. Cheng, H. Li, Q. Zhang, C. Xiao, Y. Xie, Designing a redox heterojunction for photocatalytic “overall nitrogen fixation” under mild conditions, *Adv. Mater.* 34 (2022) 2200563.
- [37] C. Dong, Y. Wang, Z. Deng, W. Wang, M. Marinova, K. Ben Tayeb, J.C. Morin, M. Dubois, M. Trentesaux, Y.G. Kolyagin, M.N. Tran, V. Martin-Diaconescu, O. Safonova, J. Zaffran, A.Y. Khodakov, V.V. Ordomsky, Photocatalytic dihydroxylation of light olefins to glycols by water, *Nat. Commun.* 15 (2024) 8210.
- [38] M. Synowiec, M. Radecka, A. Micek-Ilnicka, UV light enhanced catalytic performance of heteropolyacid-TiO₂ systems, *J. Catal.* 417 (2023) 481–496.
- [39] Y. Orooji, B. Tanhaei, A. Ayati, S.H. Tabrizi, M. Alizadeh, F.F. Bamoharram, F. Karimi, S. Salmanpour, J. Rouhi, S. Afshar, M. Sillanpää, R. Darabi, H. Karimi-Maleh, Heterogeneous UV-Switchable Au nanoparticles decorated tungstophosphoric acid/TiO₂ for efficient photocatalytic degradation process, *Chemosphere* 281 (2021) 130795.
- [40] Y. Wang, C. Dong, M. Shamzhy, M. Marinova, Z. Guo, Y.G. Kolyagin, J. Zaffran, A. Khodakov, V.V. Ordomsky, Stoichiometric selective carbonylation of methane to acetic acid by chemical looping, *ACS Catal.* 15 (2025) 3116–3125.
- [41] L. Zhang, X. Chen, Y. Ma, S. Song, H. Xu, Y. Guan, W. Song, J. Zhang, P. Wu, Single Pt coordinated with framework Fe in MWW-type ferrisilicate toward efficient propane dehydrogenation, *ACS Catal.* 14 (2024) 9431–9439.
- [42] A.J. Therrien, A.J.R. Hensley, M.D. Marcinkowski, R. Zhang, F.R. Lucci, B. Coughlin, A.C. Schilling, J.-S. McEwen, E.C.H. Sykes, An atomic-scale view of single-site Pt catalysis for low-temperature CO oxidation, *Nat. Catal.* 1 (2018) 192–198.
- [43] H. Chen, Z. Yang, X. Wang, F. Polo-Garzon, P.W. Halstenberg, T. Wang, X. Suo, S.-Z. Yang, H.M. Meyer III, Z. Wu, S. Dai, Photoinduced strong metal-support interaction for enhanced catalysis, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 143 (2021) 8521–8526.
- [44] K.I. Hadjiivanov, M.M. Kantcheva, D.G. Klissurski, IR study of CO adsorption on Cu-ZSM-5 and CuO/SiO₂ catalysts: σ and π components of the Cu+—CO bond, *J. Chem. Soc. Faraday Trans.* 92 (1996) 4595–4600.
- [45] K.I. Hadjiivanov, G.N. Vayssilov, Characterization of oxide surfaces and zeolites by carbon monoxide as an IR probe molecule, *Adv. Catal. Acad. Press* (2002) 307–511.
- [46] X. Yang, M. Li, L. Xu, F. Li, Limitation of WO₃ in Zn-Co₃O₄ nanopolyhedra by the Pyrolysis of H₃PW₁₂O₄₀@BMZIF: synergistic effect of heterostructure and oxygen vacancies for enhanced nitrogen fixation, *Inorg. Chem.* 62 (2023) 8710–8718.
- [47] Y. He, H. Rao, K. Song, J. Li, Y. Yu, Y. Lou, C. Li, Y. Han, Z. Shi, S. Feng, 3D hierarchical ZnIn₂S₄ nanosheets with rich Zn vacancies boosting photocatalytic CO₂ reduction, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* 29 (2019) 1905153.
- [48] N. Lakshmi, S. Chandra, Proton conducting composites of heteropolyacid hydrates (Phosphomolybdic and Phosphotungstic Acids) dispersed with insulating Al₂O₃, *Phys. Status Solidi (a)* 186 (2001) 383–399.
- [49] D. Sidorczuk, M. Kozanecki, B. Civalieri, K. Pernal, J. Prywer, Structural and optical properties of struvite. elucidating structure of infrared spectrum in high frequency range, *J. Phys. Chem. A* 124 (2020) 8668–8678.
- [50] C. Pază, S. Bordiga, A. Zecchina, H₂O Interaction with Solid H₃PW₁₂O₄₀: an IR Study, *Langmuir* 16 (2000) 8139–8144.
- [51] K. Coenen, F. Gallucci, B. Mezari, E. Hensen, M. van Sint Annaland, An in-situ IR study on the adsorption of CO₂ and H₂O on hydrocalcites, *J. CO₂ Util.* 24 (2018) 228–239.
- [52] D. Dvoranová, M. Mazúr, I. Papailias, T. Giannakopoulou, C. Trapalis, V. Brezová, EPR investigations of G-C₃N₄/TiO₂ nanocomposites, *Catalysts* 8 (2018) 47.
- [53] S. Kuba, P. Lukinskas, R.K. Grasselli, B.C. Gates, H. Knözinger, Structure and properties of tungstated zirconia catalysts for alkane conversion, *J. Catal.* 216 (2003) 353–361.

- [54] R. Bliem, J. van der Hoeven, A. Zavodny, O. Gamba, J. Pavelec, P.E. deJongh, M. Schmid, U. Diebold, G.S. Parkinson, An atomic-scale view of CO and H₂ oxidation on a Pt/Fe₃O₄ model catalyst, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 54 (2015) 13999–14002.
- [55] N. Rothermel, H.-H. Limbach, I. del Rosal, R. Poteau, G. Mencia, B. Chaudret, G. Buntkowsky, T. Gutmann, Surface reactions of ammonia on ruthenium nanoparticles revealed by ¹⁵N and ¹³C solid-state NMR, *Catal. Sci. Technol.* 11 (2021) 4509–4520.
- [56] P. Bertani, J. Raya, B. Bechinger, ¹⁵N chemical shift referencing in solid state NMR, *Solid State Nucl. Magn. Reson.* 61 62 (2014) 15–18.
- [57] I. Szewczyk, A. Rokicińska, M. Michalik, J. Chen, A. Jaworski, R. Aleksis, A.J. Pell, N. Hedin, A. Slabon, P. Kuśtrowski, Electrochemical denitrification and oxidative dehydrogenation of ethylbenzene over N-doped mesoporous carbon: atomic level understanding of catalytic activity by ¹⁵N NMR spectroscopy, *Chem. Mater.* 32 (2020) 7263–7273.
- [58] D. Li, Y. Zhao, Y. Miao, C. Zhou, L.-P. Zhang, L.-Z. Wu, T. Zhang, Accelerating electron-transfer dynamics by TiO₂-immobilized reversible single-atom copper for enhanced artificial photosynthesis of urea, *Adv. Mater.* 34 (2022) 2207793.
- [59] Z. Tian, Y. Da, M. Wang, X. Dou, X. Cui, J. Chen, R. Jiang, S. Xi, B. Cui, Y. Luo, H. Yang, Y. Long, Y. Xiao, W. Chen, Selective photoelectrochemical oxidation of glucose to glucaric acid by single atom Pt decorated defective TiO₂, *Nat. Commun.* 14 (2023) 142.
- [60] J. Chang, M.J. Hülsey, S. Wang, M. Li, X. Ma, N. Yan, Electrothermal water-gas shift reaction at room temperature with a silicomolybdate-based palladium single-atom catalyst, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 62 (2023) e202218265.
- [61] Q.-Q. Fan, C.-G. Niu, H. Guo, D.-W. Huang, Z.-T. Dong, Y.-Y. Yang, H.-Y. Liu, L. Li, M.-Z. Qin, Insights into the role of reactive oxygen species in photocatalytic H₂O₂ generation and OTC removal over a novel BN/Zn₃In₂S₆ heterojunction, *J. Hazard. Mater.* 438 (2022) 129483.
- [62] Y.-Y. Yang, H. Guo, D.-W. Huang, L. Li, H.-Y. Liu, L. Sui, Q. Wu, J.-J. Zhu, L. Zhang, C.-G. Niu, Simultaneously tuning oxygen reduction pathway and charge transfer dynamics toward sacrificial agent-free photocatalytic H₂O₂ production for in-situ water disinfection, *Chem. Eng. J.* 479 (2024) 147863.
- [63] H.-Y. Liu, C.-G. Niu, D.-W. Huang, H. Guo, M.-K. Li, Y.-Y. Yang, N. Tang, L. Li, L. Zhang, Synergy between sulfur vacancy and Schottky junction into CoB/ZnIn₂S₄-S photocatalysts: oriented charge flow and regulated carriers transfer dynamics to activate reactive oxygen species generation for efficient photocatalytic disinfection, *J. Clean. Prod.* 387 (2023) 135742.
- [64] Y.-Y. Yang, H.-P. Feng, X.-G. Zhang, H. Guo, X.-J. Wen, L. Sui, Z.-T. Dong, M. Yan, C.-G. Niu, Regulating and protecting of oxygen vacancy endow MoO₃-x@Zn₂In₂S₅ S-scheme core-shell heterojunction with high-efficiency organic pollutant removal and bacterial disinfection: correlation of pollutant active sites to degradation pathways, *Chem. Eng. J.* 490 (2024) 151309.
- [65] Y. Zhao, L. Zheng, R. Shi, S. Zhang, X. Bian, F. Wu, X. Cao, G.I.N. Waterhouse, T. Zhang, Alkali etching of layered double hydroxide nanosheets for enhanced photocatalytic N₂ reduction to NH₃, *Adv. Energy Mater.* 10 (2020) 2002199.